

ABDULLOH IBN MUBORAKNING ASARLARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur tadqiqot islom ilm-fanining yuksak namoyandalaridan biri bo'lgan Abdulloh ibn Muborakning ilmiy merosini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, u kishi tomonidan yozilgan hadisiiy, fiqhiy, tafsiriiy, tarixiiy va axloqiiy asarlar ilk manbaalarga tayangan holda chuqur tahlil etiladi. Tadqiqotda Ibn an-Nadim, Ibn al-Javziy, Muhammad ibn Ja'far al-Qattoni kabi manbalarda zikr etilgan o'n birta muhim asar ko'rib chiqilgan bo'lib, ularning har biri islom ilmlarining shakllanishida tutgan o'rni, tematik yo'nalishi, mazmuniiy va uslubiiy xususiiyatlari bilan o'rganiladi.

Tadqiqotda ayniqsa "Kitob az-Zuhd var-Raqoiq" asarining tarkibiiy tuzilmasi, unda keltirilgan hadislar, tobein va salaflardan rivoyat etilgan hikmatlar, tasavvufiiy-axloqiiy g'oyalar tahlil qilinadi. Bu asarning 16 bobdan iborat bo'lib, har bir bob bir necha bo'limlardan tashkil topgani, va unda iymon, tavba, dunyo va oxirat, sabr, taqvo kabi mavzular yoritilgani ko'rsatiladi. Ibn Muborakning bu asarni o'qiyotgan paytdagi ruhiy holati, uni eshitganlar tomonidan qanday taassurot qoldirgani haqidagi tarixiiy guvohliklar ilmiy isbot bilan beriladi.

Muallif, shuningdek, Abdulloh ibn Muborakning "Kitob al-Jihod", "Kitob al-Tarix", "Kitob at-Tafsir" kabi asarlari haqida mavjud bo'lgan tarixiiy manbalarni jamlab, ularning ilmiy-nazariy ahamiiyatini yoritadi. Tadqiqotda Imom al-Buxoriiy va boshqa buyuk muhaddislarning Ibn Muborak asarlaridan ilhomlanganliklari, ularning bu asarlarni eshitib yod olganliklari haqida dalillar keltirilgan.

Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari nafaqat hadis ilmi va islom madaniiy merosining tarixiiy rivojlanish jarayonini oydinlashtiradi, balki bugungi kunda ham axloqiiy-ma'naviiy tarbiya, diniy bilimlarning manbaasi sifatida ushbu asarlarning ahamiiyatini namoyon etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Abdulloh ibn Muborak, hadis ilmi, zuhd va tasavvuf, islomiiy axloq, ilmiy meros, ilmiy-munozarali tahlil

WORKS OF ABDULLAH IBN MUBARAK

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Abstract: This study is devoted to the study of the scientific heritage of Abdullah ibn Mubarak, one of the prominent figures of Islamic science, and the hadith, jurisprudential, exegetical, historical and ethical works written by him are analyzed in depth based on primary sources. The study examines eleven important works mentioned in sources such as Ibn an-Nadim, Ibn al-Jawzi, Muhammad ibn Ja'far al-Qattani, and each of them is studied in terms of its role in the formation of Islamic sciences, its thematic direction, content and methodological features.

The study analyzes in particular the structural structure of the work "Kitab az-Zuhd var-Raqaiq", the hadiths cited in it, wisdoms narrated from the followers and predecessors, and mystical and moral ideas. It is shown that this work consists of 16 chapters, each chapter consists of several sections, and it covers topics such as faith, repentance, this world and the hereafter, patience, and piety. Historical testimonies about Ibn Mubarak's mental state while reading this work and the impression he made on those who heard it are given with scientific

evidence. The author also summarizes the available historical sources about Abdullah ibn Mubarak's works such as "Kitab al-Jihad", "Kitab al-Tarikh", "Kitab at-Tafsir" and highlights their scientific and theoretical significance. The study provides evidence that Imam al-Bukhari and other great hadith scholars were inspired by the works of Ibn Mubarak, and that they memorized these works after hearing them.

The results of this study not only clarify the historical development of the science of hadith and Islamic cultural heritage, but also demonstrate the importance of these works as a source of moral and spiritual education and religious knowledge today.

Keywords: Abdullah ibn Mubarak, science of hadith, asceticism and mysticism, Islamic ethics, scientific heritage, scientific and debatable analysis.

KIRISH

Movarounnahrda hadis ilmi vujudga kelgan paytdan boshlab muhaddis olimlarning ilm izlab boshqa mamlakatlarga sayohat qilishi ikki daryo oralig'idagi o'lkalarda hadis ilmining rivojlanishiga asosiy sabab bo'lgan. Tarixiy manbalarga ko'ra, VIII asr o'rtalaridan XV asrgacha Movarounnahrning ko'pgina shaharlarida minglab muhaddislar faoliyat yuritgan. Hadis ilmi mazhabi rivojida bir qancha muhaddislar, jumladan, Abdulloh ibn Muborakning xizmatlari juda katta. Movonuahirda hadis maktablarining rivojlanishi asosida dunyoga mashhur bir qancha muhaddislar yetishib chiqdi. Bu davr muhaddis allomalarining samarali mehnatlari ilm olishdek ezgu mehnatni ro'yobga chiqarishlari natijasidir. Hukmdorlar ulamolarga mehribon va hurmatli edilar, chunki Islom dinidan boshqa din yo'q edi.

Abdulloh ibn Muborak Rabboniy ulamolarga xos bo'lgan ixlos, taqvo, ilm va amalda o'z zamondoshlari orasida yetakchi bo'lgan, ilm olish va yetkazishda juda talabchan edi. Din ta'limotlarini, Payg'ambar (s.a.v)ning hadislarini asrab-avaylash va yetkazish yo'lida tinimsiz mehnat qildi.

Uning allomalar va boshqalar nazdida tutgan o'rni haqida gapirilar ekan, bu buyuk allomaning ijodini o'rganish zaruriyati anglab yetiladi. Chunki ajdodlarning hayot yo'li, ilmiy merosini o'rganishdan maqsad ham ajdodlar hayotini namuna qilib, bilimli va dono yoshlarni tarbiyalash, tarixda islom diniga poydevor qo'ygan o'tmishdagi ajdodlar yoshlariga ibrat bo'lishdir.

Imom Muhammad ibn Ismoil al-Buxoriy birinchi marta hadisni eshitgan va Ibn Muborakning tasniflarini yod olgan yosh bola edi. U aytdi: "Men o'n olti yoshligimda Abdulloh ibn Muborak Marvaziy (vafoti 798) va Vakiy ibn al-Jarroh ibn Mulayh ar-Ravaviy (vafoti 814) kitoblarini o'qidim, uni to'liq yod olib, ota-onamning so'zlarini ham o'rgandim, so'ng u as'hobga ketdim.

Ahmad "Ibn an-Nadim "Hadis sahobalarining fuqahosi haqida xabarlar" oltinchi bobida Ibn al-Muborakning kitoblari sifatida quyidagi kitoblarni zikr qiladi: 1. "Sunan fil-fiqh" kitobi.

2. "Kitob at-tafsir" (Kitob tafsir),
3. "Kitob at-tarix" (Tarix kitobi),
4. "Kitob al-birri vas-sila" (Yaxshilik va rahm-shafqat kitobi),
5. "Kitob az-zuhd var-raqoiq" (Kitob taqvo va ilohiyot).
6. "Musnsd", "Kitabu al-jihod", "Arbain".
7. "Rikoul al-fatava".

Muhammad ibn Ja'far al-Kattani al-Fosiy "Kitob al-Istazon" ("Ijzat kitobi")ni Ibn al-

Muborakning kitobi deb atagan. Bu kitob durdona asarlardan biridir.

Ibn al-Javziy aytadiki, Ibn Muborak “Kitob al-manasik” (“Namoz qoidalari kitobi”)ni Kufada yozgan.

O’n bir kitob Abdulloh ibn al-Muborak tomonidan tasniflangan, ammo hoziri paytgacha ular haqida hech qanday ma’lumot yetib kelmagan. Sakkizinchi kitob yo’qolgan bo’lsa kerak. Vaholanki, “Kitob az-zuhd var-raqoiq” kitobi 1966-yilda Hindistondagi “Ihyo al-Maorif” nashriyotida chop etilgan. Bu kitob Habib ar-Rahmon al-Azam tomonidan tadqiq qilingan. Bu kitobda Payg’ambar (s.a.v) va sahobalarining hikmatlar, ma’ruzalar, masalalar, axloq, Alloh taoloning marhamati, tavbaning qabul qilinishi, yolg’on va riyokorlikni qoralash, musibatlariga chidash haqida hadislar keltirilgan. , bo’ysunuvchilarning asarlari to’plangan.

Darhaqiqat, Ibn Muborak jehod haqida birinchi kitob yozgan. Demak, u birinchi bo’lib taqvo va ilohiyot haqida kitob yozgan. Ibn al-Muborakning “Kitob az-zuhd var-raqoiq” kitobida hadislardan quyidagi mavzular keltirilgan: -tobein”,

“Al-Marfuat a’la as-sahobati bima’ fiyhi aqvoluhum va a’olihum”, “Al-Mavqufat a’lat-tobein va atboihim”.

Kitob 16 bobdan iborat. Har bir bo’lim bir nechta bo’limlardan iborat. Birinchi qismning boblari: Alloh taologa qattiq itoat qilishga manfaatdorlik, dunyodan yuz o’girish uchun ilm zarurligi va boshqa masalalar. Ibn al-Muborak bu kitobni o’qiyotganda juda hayajonlangan edi. Al-Xatib al-Bag’dodiy aytadi: Naim ibn Hamad aytdilar: Ibn al-Muborak “Kitob az-zuhd var-raqoiq” kitobini o’qiganda, uning yig’lashi ho’kizning bo’kirishiga o’xshardi.

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